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The Ability to Manage Future Teachers' Own Resources Formation

Tatyana P. Gordienko (a), Tatyana A. Bezusova* (b), Anna I. Mezentseva (c)

(a) Crimean Engineering and Pedagogical University named after Fevzi Yakubov, Simferopol (Russia), 8 trans.Ychebnyy, (b) Perm State University, Perm (Russia), 15 Bukireva street, tabezusova@gmail.com, (c) Black Sea Higher Naval Order of the Red Star School named after P. S. Nakhimov, Sevastopol (Russia), 1a Dybenko street

Abstract

The problem of the research. The ability to manage time, build and implement the self-development path is the universal future teacher competence, reflected in the new educational standards. The question how to ensure the abilities formation associated with managing one's own person's resources (time management, stress management, self-presentation) arises. The interdisciplinary integration of some psychology and management sections provides the necessary student's self-motivation, planning their own activities, decision making and control. The self-management skills' demand in the professional teachers' activities, and, accordingly, the need to focus attention on the educational organizations administration are considered in the works of Galaguzova and Dorokhova (2017). In these works, the incorporating forms necessity, methods and means into the educational process that promote the knowledge's development, skills and abilities for future teachers to maximize the use of their own capabilities are stated.

The purpose of this study is an experimental verification of the effectiveness of the developed organizational and methodological conditions that ensure effective management of their own resources by future teachers

Theoretical methods are used for the interpretation, analysis and generalization of the theoretical principles and empirical data (theoretical analysis of pedagogical sources, comparison, specification and generalization); empirical methods are used for the creation, collection and organization of educational activities' products (observation, written survey, experiential training); mathematical methods are correlation analysis.

The discipline Effective Self-Management purpose is to form future teacher's competencies, thanks to which he or she can become the professional tasks subject, the subject of his or her own development. The following points are mandatory for the study: social control, volitional regulation, stress management, coping strategies, self-projection and time management. The course teaching is based on the problem educational technology and independent work technology. The authors of the article developed an organizational and methodological model for conducting the course Effective Self-Management. The main developed model's principles are: students' independent activity, heuristic training and training modularity. To determine the model effectiveness in the 2019-20 school year, experimental work was carried out in which pedagogical direction students of the State Pedagogical Institute (Solikamsk) and CPEU named after Fevzi Yakubov (Simferopol). The personal ability assessment was determined using the test Personal Competence in Time (Vodopyanova, 2009) and the questionnaire Copying Strategies (Vodopyanova, 2009). After the

* Corresponding author. E-mail: tabezusova@gmail.com

behavior of the Effective Self-Management course, the number of students with high personal competence in time is increased, an increase in self-control and planning skills are noted. The experiment's results showed a direct correlation between the success of training on the course Effective Self-Management and the personal, temporary and psychological resources of students.

Keywords: self-management, future teacher, interdisciplinary integration, educational content.

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Introduction

The ability to manage the time, build and implement the path of self-development on the basis of educational principles during the course of a lifetime is the universal competence (UC) of the future teacher, reflected in the new educational standards (UC-6). In the approximate basic educational programs in the field of preparation 44.00.00 *Educational and Pedagogical Sciences* (Trubina, 2019), this competency is reduced through the prism of indicators: the ability to evaluate personal resources in order to achieve the goals of managing the time in the process of realizing the self-development path; the ability to explain ways of planning free time and designing the trajectory of professional and personal growth (Trubina, 2019).

The demand for self-management skills in the professional activities of teachers and, accordingly, the need to focus the administration of educational organizations on the introduction of the self-organization foundations and personality self-development in the educational content are considered in the works of Parakhina and Perov (2012), Galaguzova and Dorokhova (2017), Klimova (2017) and others. In these works, the need for the inclusion in the educational process of forms, methods and tools that promote the development of future teachers' knowledge, skills, allowing the most efficient use of their own capabilities are stated.

Purpose and objectives of the study

Theoretically substantiate and develop educational and methodological support for the rational organization of the future teachers' work, ensuring effective management of their own resources and assessment.

Literature review

Based on the research of (Trubina, 2019) self-management is "... a system of activity methods that allows you to maximize the abilities, consciously and rationally manage life, and actively and effectively influence external circumstances at work and in the personal life for your own purposes. The approach to self-management as a technology makes it possible to apply the methods of general management to the professional activity and personal life of each person" (p. 5).

Galaguzova and Dorokhova (2017) relate to the constituent elements of self-management:

- knowledge of how to effectively manage the life;
- a system of skills to effectively manage the life;
- experience in creative activity that allows to solve effectively a variety of problems in the process of managing the life;
- experience and norms of emotional and volitional attitude to the world, to each other in the process of managing the life.

Klimova (2017) having analyzed eight approaches to the definition of self-management, speaks about the self-management in a broad sense, as practical methods of work in everyday practice, a factor contributing to the self-development of managerial activity's subjects.

Based on the presented author's points of view, we have to admit that self-management is an integrative characteristic of psychological and managerial content.

Purpose of the study. Theoretically substantiate and develop organizational and methodological conditions for training future teachers in the effective management of their own resources and their assessment

Methodology

Theoretical methods are used for the interpretation, analysis and generalization of theoretical principles and empirical data (theoretical analysis of pedagogical sources, comparison, specification and generalization); empirical methods are used for the creation, collection and organization of educational activities' products (observation, written survey and experimental training).

We decompose the competence of UC-6: Know: personality psychology, mechanisms and factors of its development, methods of self-diagnosis of personality development; psychology of activity and behavior; effective planning techniques; psychology of stress, emotions and techniques of mental self-regulation. Be able to: act critically, perform analysis of the work done to achieve the goal; plan the activities (draw up a general plan for upcoming activities, determine the sequence of actions, and organize a workplace and temporary organization of activities); to predict the result of the activities. Apply: methods of personality self-diagnosis development, methods and techniques of project activities and time management; methods of organizing educational, professional and leisure activities (Klimova, 2017). Once again, we note the need for the synthesis of psychological and managerial content for the category formation of the self-organization and self-development. Perm State National Research University proposes to solve the problem by introducing a separate course *Effective Self-Management* in the curricula of all areas (including pedagogical) of the first courses. The purpose of the discipline *Effective Self-Management* is to form future teacher's competencies, thanks to which he or she can become the subject of professional tasks, the subject of his or her own development. The sections required are social control, volitional regulation, stress management, coping strategies, self-presentation and time management. The interdisciplinary integration of some sections of psychology and management provides the necessary self-motivation of the student, planning the activities, decision making and control. The approximate content of the course *Effective Self-Management* was developed at Perm State National Research University: the basics of self-management, arbitrary forms of mental and social control, self-identification of a person, soft skills, volitional regulation of personality, time management, goal-setting, planning technology, stress management and self-presentation. Note that on open educational platforms (for example, *Open Education*) there is a sufficient number of courses that help students to develop a knowledge course in time management, career planning, teamwork, goal setting, self-motivation, burnout, stress management, etc. The course *Self-Management*, the course *Emotional Intelligence*, the course *Personal Efficiency: Time Management* (Educational platform "Open Education". Access Mode: <https://openedu.ru>) is a list of courses that to some extent meet the content of the discipline *Effective Self-Management*. Every student of any educational organization can register on the educational platform and get acquainted with the course materials.

Organizational and methodological conditions:

1. Training sessions should be aimed at identifying possible difficulties in planning the students' activities and how to overcome them, taking into account all aspects of the studied phenomenon and influencing factors; a skill formation systematic assessment of developing non-standard solutions in conditions when alternative options for actions are unclear or doubtful;
2. Each practical lesson should be result-oriented and require a quick reaction to changes in the situation, independent adoption of effective decisions in the face of a time shortage.
3. Classroom activities should end with reflection, testing the ability to introspection, an objective assessment of their actions and the ability to maximize the positive experience.

Results

A similar process of self-management clearly demonstrates the relationship between the individual functions of self-management (Galaguzova & Dorokhova, 2017):

- goal setting (personal goal analysis and formation);
- planning (plan development and alternative options for the activities);
- decision making (making decisions on upcoming matters);
- implementation and organization (preparation of the daily routine and organization of the personal labor process for the task implementation);
- control (self-control and result control (if necessary, goal adjustments);
- information and communication (search and exchange of information, the implementation of communication links necessary at all phases of the self-management process).

For each function, working methods and methods for its implementation can be developed. The conceptual foundations of the work rational organization on mastering the basics of effective self-management are: the practical involvement of students in the study and discussion of the stress state characteristics, resistance to stress, and coping strategies. Studying the stress state, coping strategies using psycho diagnostic tools in school and extracurricular times and receiving feedback on the results. Discussion of research arouses genuine interest and engagement among students. Practical training in stress management technologies and

self-regulation of emotional states are also carried out as part of training sessions in the course of the discipline Psychology.

We will give the examples of practical training sessions.

Example 1, Topic: Stress. Emotional States (table 1).

Key words: stress, causes of stress.

Plan: Studying basic theoretical questions. Registration on the Open Education Platform. Acquaintance with the course Self-management (<https://openedu.ru/course/urfu/SMNGM/>). The study of Section 5. Personal Effectiveness and Stress Resistance. The implementation of the practical part.

Table 1

Stress. Emotional States	
Key Theoretical Questions	Practical Tasks
1. Stress. 2. Pre-examination stress. Signs typical anxieties. Fear of error. Self-regulation. 3. Self-regulation of emotions (the concept of emotion, basic emotions, physiology, emotions, expression). 4. The system of emotional self-regulation, how to cope with the feelings. 5. Techniques of mindfulness.	1. Create a glossary of basic terms on theoretical issues. 2. Perform practice-oriented tasks (three situations on the Open Education Platform are proposed).

Example 2, Topic: Self-Presentation (Table 2).

Key words: self-presentation skills, types of self-presentation, career planning, resume.

Work plan: Studying the main theoretical issues. Studying the Career Planning section of the Self-Management Course (Open Education educational platform). Accomplishment of a practical task.

Table 2

Self-presentation

Key Theoretical Questions	Practical Tasks
<p>1. Self-presentation. Classifications of types, tactics and strategies of personal self-presentation.</p> <p>2. Means of personality self-presentation.</p> <p>3. Conscious and unconscious personality self-presentation.</p> <p>4. Direct and indirect personality self-presentation.</p> <p>5. Self-presentation of a person in the space of Internet communications (account analysis).</p> <p>6. Self-presentation of personality as a means of managing impression.</p>	<p>Task 1. Surf the educational platform https://openedu.ru/course/urfu/SMNGM/</p> <p>Course Self-Management. Study the section Self-Management, as a Technology. Career Planning. Complete all test tasks and practice exercises in this section.</p> <p>Task 2. Present a photograph of one week and identify the loss of personal time.</p> <p>Task 3. Study an example of a resume and evaluate the proposed criteria.</p> <p>Task 4. Write a resume.</p>

The product of students' independent activity is intelligence cards / mental cards (Gordienko & Smirnova, 2018), multidimensional didactic tools (Gordienko & Gorbunova, 2016), work with scientific sources according to a previously outlined plan, drawing up a support / structural-didactic scheme for the material under study, writing prospectuses, essays and compiling self-diagnostic notes.

Fig. 1. Mental Map Distribution of Time (prepared by the first-year student's studying in the direction of Pedagogical Education, profile Preschool and Primary Education)

Fig. 2 Mental Map Combination of Work and Rest (prepared by the first-year students studying in the direction of Pedagogical Education, profile Preschool and Primary Education)

Fig. 3 Summary Plan on the Topic Self-presentation, (prepared by the first-year students studying in the direction of Pedagogical Education, profile Preschool and Primary Education).

Heuristic training is implemented through the creation of problem situations, the expansion of one's own experience, the organization of interdisciplinary relations, the object of search activity are the student's own experience. The modularity of training is realized through differentiation of the discipline's content and the integration of the material through lectures "together" (two lecturers). A compulsory element of education is the students' group preparation for workshops on quick reading, memory training, methods of scientific taking notes, long-term planning technology, etc. At the end of each lecture, students are to answer questions in writing. For example, after studying the topic *Social Control*, students answer the questions: What are the elements of social control? Describe the network of social relations and the system of social interaction. What is the difference between external and internal control? What are the control methods? What is the mechanism for the public opinion formation and functioning? When studying the topic *Personal Identity*, students are encouraged to diagnose self-esteem and determine their locus control.

In order to determine the effectiveness of the model in the 2019-2020 academic year, experimental work was carried out in which pedagogical directions students of the State Pedagogical Institute took part (Solikamsk). The assessment of personal abilities was determined using the test Personal Competency in Time (Vodopyanova, 2009) and the questionnaire Copying Strategies (Vodopyanova, 2009). The data of the experimental group are presented (see tab. 4 and tab. 5, tab. 6, tab. 7, fig. 4)

Test Personal Competence in Time

(before teaching the piece Effective Self-Management)

Member Number	The level of personal competence over time (stating slice) 02/03/2020	The level of personal competence over time (control slice) 04/22/2020
1	not enough	high
2	not enough	medium
3	not enough	medium
4	not enough	medium
5	law	high
6	law	high
7	law	high
8	law	high
9	law	high

10	law	high
11	law	high
12	law	high
13	high	high

Table 5

Summary table of personal competence over time (ascertaining slice)

Competency Level	Ascending Slice	Control Slice
not enough	30,8%	-
law	61,5%	-
medium	-	23%
high	7,7%	77%

Fig. 4. The Results of Stating and Control Sections Comparison of the Experimental Group (Control and Stating Sections)

Table 6

Interpretation of the Copying Strategies Questionnaire

(Ascertaining Slice)

	high	medium	low
Confrontational coping	15,4%	76,9%	7.7%
Distance	30,8%	61,5%	7.7 %
Self control	23,1%	76,9%	-

Social support search	15,4%	84,6%	-
Acceptance of responsibility	69,2%	23,1%	7,7%
Escape	53,6%	46,4%	-
Problem planning	23,1%	76,9%	-
Positive revaluation	53,9%	46,1%	-

Table 7

Interpretation of the Questionnaire Copying strategies (Control Slice)

	high	medium	low
Confrontational coping	30,7%	46,2%	23,1%
Distance	23,1	61,5%	15,4%
Self control	53,8%	46,2%	-
Social support search	30,7%	69,3%	-

Acceptance of responsibility	69,2%	30,8%	-
Escape	46,1%	38,5%	15,4%
Problem planning	46,1%	53,9%	-
Positive revaluation	76,9%	23,1%	-

After the Effective Self-Management Course conduction, the number of students with high personal competence has increased; an increase in self-control and planning skills, the prevalence of such copings as “positive revaluation”, “responsibility acceptance” are noted. The results of the experiment showed a direct correlation between the success of training on the course Effective Self-Management and the personal, temporary and psychological resources of the students. Therefore, we conclude that the course Effective Self-Management has a positive effect on the competence formation of self-organization and self-realization of the students personality of higher education organizations.

Discussions

The question arises how to ensure the ability formation associated with managing one’s own person’s resources (time management, stress management and self-presentation) and their assessment. Firstly, modern normative documents regulating Russian education actualize the problem of including the self-management’s basics in the content of higher education. There is a need to determine the curricula resources of all profiles and areas to provide content related to a person’s self-organization and self-development. Secondly, the variety of self-management functions (self-motivation, planning of one’s own activities, decision-making, implementation and organization, control, information and communication (Parakhina & Perov, 2012) will determine the difficulty in choosing a teacher who oversees the course of basic self-management for students.

Conclusion

To ensure students' self-realization and self-development of future teachers, it is possible to offer an introduction to the discipline's curriculum (elective course), focused on studying the self-management basics. As a result of mastering such a course, students learn the specifics of the *self-management* concept and its components, are able to differentiate time management and stress management, acquire the skills of evaluating their own temporary, personal, psychological resources to achieve the goal, formulates the prospect of developing their own. During the study, it was confirmed that the material and tasks described in the article contribute to the formation of students' skills such as: analysis of the work done, planning their own activities, predicting the results of activities and time management.

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